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E-CIGARETTE CONSUMPTION AMONG FEMALE STUDENTS OF FACULTY OF PHARMACY, NOVI SAD – KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES AND PRACTICES

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Worrying data on cigarette consumption is increasingly triggering a public debate on public health policy and youth education as part of addiction prevention.

Objectives: The paper will present the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of female pharmacy students regarding the consumption of e-cigarettes.

Materials and methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted using an original questionnaire distributed through the Google platform.

Results: The survey included 193 respondents. All respondents heard about e-cigarettes, 32.6% from social networks and electronic media, and 30.6% from the university; 53.4% of respondents have tried, and 31.6% currently use e-cigarettes and/or tobacco cigarettes. About 70% of respondents started smoking e-cigarettes to protect their/family members health. 52.5% to avoid the ban on smoking in public places, and only 21.3% for economic reasons; 99.0% believe that smoking e-cigarettes is harmful to health; 18.6% believe that e-cigarettes are less harmful than tobacco cigarettes; 52.3% of respondents believe that e-cigarettes do not represent a lower risk of cancer compared to tobacco cigarettes; and 73.8% expressed their desire to stop smoking cigarettes in the future.

Conclusion: The proven harmfulness of conventional and e-cigarettes to health, with special implications for the female population, should encourage new research and smoking prevention strategies.

Key words: e-cigarettes, addictions, female pharmacy students, knowledge, practices